

CH30220/CH40220: Chemistry Thermodynamics in Context

Coursework: Scientific Commentary

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Your ability to hear relies on active cochlear frequency amplification

- **Practice:** Targeted therapies for hearing loss are made possible by a greater understanding of cochlear physiology, particularly for those with cochlear protein mutations.
- **Research:** Further studies should elucidate the distribution of ion-channels within the cochlear hair cells, possibly identifying new targets to treat genetic forms of deafness.

The mammalian cochlea demonstrates biological thermodynamics in action as it is converting sound waves into neural signals, through energy-dependent processes. This spiral-shaped organ contains two types of sensory cells: outer hair cells (OHCs) and inner hair cells (IHCs) (figure 1). OHCs amplify sound vibrations that enter the ear and IHCs convert these vibrations into neural signals. OHCs and IHCs both operate via ion-gradients, generated by ATP-driven pumps. However, disruptions in these energy-dependent processes (active processes), due to genetic mutations or metabolic stress, can incur hearing loss¹. This commentary explores cochlear biomechanics, as reviewed by Ashmore, focusing on the role of prestin in this energy transduction system.

Fig. 1 Outer hair cell (left) and inner hair cell (right) (adapted from [1]).

Ashmore uses biophysical and molecular methods to interrogate the cochlea's function. Laser interferometry measured nanoscale vibrations of the basilar membrane and patch-clamp electrophysiology characterised the voltage dependent protein, prestin, within OHCs. A subtractive cDNA library and knockout model identified prestin's role in electromotility. Freeze-fracture studies and

immunohistochemistry characterised potassium ion channels (i.e. KCNQ4) and prestin proteins in hair cell membranes. Genomic analyses correlated mutations in prestin and KCNQ4 to hearing losses. Functional assays, in systems such as transfected kidney cells, investigated prestin's electromechanical properties. Ashmore's methods revealed how ion gradients and voltage-induced protein changes enable cochlear amplification.

Ashmore reveals how thermodynamic principles govern cochlear amplification and signal transduction. OHCs, which contain prestin, a protein that converts electrical energy into mechanical work, also contain stereocilia (small hair bundles), on their cell membrane. When sound waves enter the cochlea, the stereocilia on the OHCs deflect, opening mechano-electrical transducer (MET) channels. This enables potassium ions (K^+) to flow into the cells, depolarising them. Prestin detects this change in voltage and changes shape, causing the OHC to elongate or shorten. It is this movement that amplifies basilar membrane vibrations, amplifying sound sensitivity by up to 40 dB. This comes at the cost of relying on ATP-driven pumps to maintain the cell's high K^+ concentration.

IHCs, on the other hand, convert mechanical vibrations into electrical signals. Upon vibration of the basilar membrane, the stereocilia on the IHCs deflect, opening-up the MET channels, allowing K^+ to flow within. The IHC becomes depolarised, causing a neurotransmitter to be released to the auditory nerve. IHCs also depend on ATP-driven pumps to maintain the potassium ion gradient. Ashmore also discusses that mutations in ion-channels like KCNQ4 can prevent K^+ flow from OHCs, inhibiting the cochlea's function, causing progressive hearing loss. Also, prestin's dependence on intracellular chloride (Cl^-) makes it susceptible to changes in ion balances. Disrupted Cl^- levels may cause hinder prestin's function, inhibiting sound amplification.

Ashmore perspicuously demonstrates how the cochlea is a complex machine where energy conversion provides us with the ability to hear, with a reliance on ion gradients and voltage changes. The cochlea's requirement for a continuous energy supply can be examined from a thermodynamic perspective. Within the hair cells, the high K^+ concentration (~150 mM) and +80 mV are maintained by ATP-driven pumps in the hair cell membrane. This voltage difference provides the necessary Gibbs free energy difference (ΔG), enabling MET to occur. This is energetically costly, with around 60 % of the cochlea's energy reserves dedicated to driving ion flux. Therefore, could Ashmore potentially address how efficient the cochlea really is? Quantifying efficiency as ($\eta = \text{work output/energy input}$), how much of the energy input actually goes towards "useful" work?

Within the cochlea, viscous damping and ion leakage are ways that energy is dissipated. For example, mutations in KCNQ4 cause entropy-driven energy loss, as dictated by the second law of thermodynamics, preventing K^+ efflux, resulting in OHC dysfunction. Likewise, prestin's reliance on Cl^- causes the same type of thermodynamic fragility, ultimately degrading prestin's efficiency. Ashmore could delve deeper into the delicate balance between energy input and output within the cochlea.

If Ashmore were to explore the underlying thermodynamic principles of the cochlea's biomechanics, this could provide opportunity for innovation. For instance, Ashmore could conduct comparative studies across different species,

not just mammalian organisms, including bats, with ultrasonic hearing, revealing how they have adapted to thermodynamic constraints, maximising system efficiency. Perhaps bats have evolved more efficient variants of prestin, or faster ion-recycling mechanisms, that would allow for amplification and signal transmission at a faster rate or to a greater extent. With this newfound knowledge, it may provide a blueprint for designing the next generation of hearing devices, with greater efficiency and lower power requirements.

Overall, Ashmore provides an in-depth overview of the cochlea's intricacies and reminds us that solutions to some of our most pressing challenges may already exist in nature, within us.

References:

1. Jonathan Ashmore. Biophysics of the Cochlea – Biomechanics and Ion Channelopathies. Br. Med. Bull. 2002, 63 (1), 59-72